

A REVIEW: EFFECT OF BIOCHAR ON SOIL HEALTH AND CROP PRODUCTIVITY

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Abstract

Recently, the use of biochar has been suggested as a management technique to increase crop yield and reduce global warming. Biochar may be added to soils with the goal to improve the soil properties and relocate an amount of conventional fossil fuel based fertilizers and sequester carbon. The establishment of biochar and its integration into soil must contribute to the mitigation of climate change. The need for further clarity on optimizing biochar application to various crop yields is necessary if it is to gain widespread acceptance as a soil amendment. There is urgent need to intensify agricultural production to secure food supply for the ever increasing population especially in developing country like India of the tropics. Developers of biochar have focused on the stability of biochar in soil, which also includes improving soil fertility and water-holding capacity, producing more crops, and cleaning up contaminated soils. Over 1 Pg of CO₂-carbon equivalents might be feasibly and sustainably sequestered or neutralized annually using biochar. The incentives provided by the current carbon market are insufficient to optimize or quickly accelerate the beginning and development of biochar implementation.

Key words:- Biochar, Carbon sequestration, Soil properties, Soil organisms, Soil amendment

Introduction

The foundation of a healthy and sustainable food system is a fertile soil. As the land is farmed, the agricultural process disturbs the natural soil systems including nutrient cycling and the release and uptake of nutrients (Skjemstad *et al.*, 2002; Lal, 2004). Efficient use of biomass, available as crop residues and other farm wastes, by converting it to a useful source of soil amendment/nutrients is one way to manage soil health and fertility (DeLuca *et al.*, 2006; Glaser *et al.*, 2001). Biochar is a potential soil amendment and carbon sequestration medium. It also reduces farm waste and improves the soil quality.

Providing wholesome food for the world's expanding population is agriculture's primary responsibility both today and in the future. But agriculture is of more significance to global climate change and its effects on soil health and crop productivity. The adoption of improved crop varieties, fertilizers, pest control techniques, and irrigation has led to high yields and enhanced food and nutritional security (Lehmann *et al.*, 2011). Despite high productivity, farmers see various problems associated with our intensive agricultural systems. It emphasizes the integration of biological, chemical and physical measures of soil quality that affect farmers profit and the environment. Utilizing crop residue-based soil amendments effectively is a key tactic for raising soil fertility and productivity in rain-fed regions.

India produces 500 Mt of crop wastes annually, of which 141 Mt are surplus. These residues are used in part or not at all because of different limitations. Surplus and unused crop residues when left unattended, often disrupt land preparation, crop establishment and early crop growth and therefore are typically burnt on farm which causes environmental problems and substantial nutrient losses (Kannan Pandian *et al.*, 2016). Efficient use of huge amount of biomasses, available as crop and agro forestry residues and other farm wastes by converting it in to a useful source of soil amendment. In this regard, biochar, an organic soil amendment, has emerged as a promising technique to mitigate climate change, preserve soil health, and assure sustainable food production on a worldwide scale.

Biochar

Biochar is a solid that is produced by thermo chemically preserving biomass in an oxygen-poor atmosphere. (IBI, 2015). Biochar is a porous, fine-grained, carbon-rich substance produced by pyrolysis of plant biomass at temperatures ranging from 350-600°C in an oxygen-free environment (Ameloot *et al.*, 2015). The word Biochar is derived from Greek word. The term "bios" refers to life, while "char" refers to charcoal. The term biochar was invented by Peter Read (lobbyists for biochar plantations). Biochar is a carbon substance produced through

pyrolysis and utilized as a soil amendment (Krull *et al.*, 2006). It is a black carbon-rich substance that is produced by heating biomass in an oxygen-starved environment. Unlike the original biomass, it contributes to long term removal of CO₂ from atmosphere, since it is chemically and biologically more stable.

Need of biochar research in India**a. Reduce the crop residue burning in the field**

Open field burning of crop residues is an age old practice to boost soil fertility in terms of P and K, but it often leads to a loss of other nutrients such as N and S, organic matter and microbial activity required for maintaining better soil health (IARI, 2012). But maintenance of threshold level of organic matter in rainfed soil is crucial to sustain soil physical, chemical and biological health. Converting agricultural and agroforestry leftovers into biochar via a thermochemical process (slow pyrolysis) is an alternate method of handling useless and extra crop residues.

b. To improve organic carbon in soil

Biochar contains organic matter and nutrients, its addition increased soil pH, EC, Organic carbon in soil and thereby improves the soil fertility.

c. To reduce CO₂ rise in atmosphere

The burning and natural decomposition of biomass and in particular agricultural waste adds large amounts of CO₂ to the atmosphere. Biochar is a stable way of storing carbon in the ground for centuries, potentially reducing or stalling the growth in atmospheric green house gas levels.

d. Environmental degradation

Biochar improves environmental quality by reducing soil nutrient leaching losses, reducing the bioavailability of environmental pollutants, sequestering carbon, lowering GHG emissions, and increasing crop yield in heavily weathered or degraded soil.

Impact of biochar on soil properties- Soil physical and chemical properties-

The physio-chemical properties are soil pH, bulk density, water holding capacity, or cation exchange capacity of soils amended with biochar are positively increased. Khaled *et al.*, (2019) conducted the field experiment in sandy soils with application of various rates of biochar *viz.*, 10, 15 and 20 t ha⁻¹ and concluded that the significantly increased water use efficiency (WUE), crop growth and water retention by 50 to 90 per cent, respectively as compared to the control like without biochar applied treatment, because the favorable effect of BC treatments on soil water retention increased with incubation time and was greatest for the low pyrolysis temperature BC (BC300). This suggested that when BC matures in soil, it becomes more effective in enhancing water retention, particularly at low pyrolysis temperatures. Patel and Yadav

(2018) conducted the experiment in sandy soils in application of RDF along with Maize stover char @ 10 t ha⁻¹ application recorded the significantly lower bulk density (1.05 g cm⁻³) and also increasing the Water holding capacity of the soil all so positively significant of 28.27 per cent, these results are confirmed with the (Castaldi *et al.*, 2011). Besides, the decrease in bulk density of biochar-amended soil could be one of the indicators of enhancement of soil structure or aggregation and aeration and could be soil-specific (Atkinson *et al.*, 2010).

Kannan Pandian *et al.*, (2016) A field experiment was carried out in Alfisol in the Semi-Arid tropics, and the results show that soil application of red gram biochar improved the field-saturated hydraulic conductivity of the sandy soil, resulting in an increase in net water usage efficiency. At the same time chemical properties of soil also alter like soil pH, total C, total N, Olson P and cation exchange capacity, because the applied biochar have more number of functional groups that are easily adsorbed the cation are strongly and increasing the nutrient availability of soils (Hong *et al.*, 2014). Snekapriya and Jayachandran (2018) performed a research trial in sugar cane crop with the application of sugarcane trash biochar @ 2 t ha⁻¹ along with grade levels fertilizer application and the results are concluded that the long-term effect on biochar, the soil properties are positively increased because the biochar will take time to mineralize and slowly released the nutrients and then crop will be easily increased uptake and availability of soils the same findings also reported by Supriya *et al.*, (2019) and Jin-Hua *et al.* (2011).

Soil biological properties-

Biochar pores and its high internal surface area which increased ability to absorb organic matter act as refuge for soil microbiota from predators and desiccation. The use of biochar enhanced the number of bacteria, actinomycetes, and arbuscular mycorrhizal fungus, which reduces nitrogen loss and increases nutrient availability for plants. The chemical stability of a major portion of a particular biochar material means that bacteria will be unable to readily utilize the carbon as an energy source, as well as the nitrogen and possibly other nutrients contained in the carbon structure.

Snekapriya and Jayachandran (2018) conducted a research trial on sugar cane with different grades of NPK (50, 75, 100, 125, 150 per cent along with Biochar @ 2 t ha⁻¹) and with biofertilizers (PSB and *Rhizobium*) in sandy soil and the results are reported that maximum microbial population was bacteria (33.16 cfu), fungi (10.25 cfu) and actinomycetes (17.44 cfu) observed in application of 150 per cent dose of NPK along with 2 t of biochar + biofertilizer @ 10 kg ha⁻¹. Segun *et al.* (2019) experimented with multiple levels of rice straw biochar application (0, 3, 6, and 12 t ha⁻¹) in sandy loam soil in Nigeria and discovered that 12 t ha⁻¹ of biochar application significantly increased soil enzyme activity. Rondon *et al.* (2007) found an increase in nitrogen fixation in *Phaseolus vulgaris*, while Chan *et al.* (2008) reported an increase in earthworm and microbial biomass. Biochar application to soil has long tradition provided evidence that it has positive effects on the abundance of mycorrhizal fungi.

Impact of biochar on soils dynamics Fertilizer use efficiency (FUE)

Understanding the function of biochar and how it interacts with crop roots and nutrients could help us better understand how efficiently fertilizer is used. In addition to lowering the overall amount of fertilizer needed, the improved nutrient retention capacity of biochar-amended soil also mitigates the effects of climate change and environmental factors on crops (Chan and Xu, 2009). Biochar significantly increases the efficiency and reduces the need for traditional chemical fertilizers with sustainable crop yields. Biochar reduces soil acidity and the requirement for some chemical and fertilizer inputs, which increases crop yields and productivity and helps to improve soil

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resources (Yeboah *et al.*, 2009). The longer-term benefits of applying biochar to the availability of nutrients are mostly attributable to increased organic matter stabilization, concurrently slower nutrient release from more organic matter, and improved cation exchange capacity, which results in higher cation retention overall. Increased plant uptake of P, K, Ca, Zn, and Cu has been related to high rates of biochar addition in tropical environments (Lehmann *et al.*, 2007).

Biological nitrogen fixation by common beans was increased from 50 to 72% of total nitrogen uptake with increasing rates of biochar additions (0, 31, 62 and 93 t ha⁻¹) to a low-fertility Oxisol (Rondon *et al.*, 2007). Additionally, according to Major *et al.* (2010), biochar adds certain macronutrients (P, K, N, Ca, and Mg) and micronutrients (Cu, Zn, Fe, and Mn) that are necessary for sustainable agriculture. It could have a major impact on nutrient retention and be essential to many different bio-geochemical processes in the soil, particularly nutrient cycling. In soils enriched with biochar, phosphorus that is available to plants has been shown to benefit from the substance, which in contrast to ammonium, is not a characteristic generally associated with soil organic matter (Lehmann *et al.*, 2007; Steiner *et al.*, 2007).

Soil nutrient leaching prevention-

Biochar has been shown to reduce nutrient leaching and increase nutrient availability (Chan *et al.*, 2007). Higher nutrient availability for plants results from both direct nutrient input by biochar and increased nutrient retention. Biochar may supply a source of plant-available nutrients once applied to the soil. The significant adsorption affinity of biochar for soluble nutrients like phosphate, ammonium, nitrate, and other ionic solutes suggests this possibility. The cumulative leaching of mineral N, K, and Mg in the soil was only 24, 45, and 7%, respectively, to control biochar, according to Lehmann *et al.*'s 2007 findings (Krishna Veni *et al.*, 2017). Results of the column leaching experiment showed that biochar addition significantly influenced Na⁺, K⁺, Ca⁺⁺ and Mg⁺⁺ concentrations in the leachate. For Na⁺ concentration, no significant difference was found with biochar amendment under non-saline irrigation compared to respective non-biochar control.

Modification of soil-

Biochar is commonly alkaline. The pH values of biochar at different pyrolysis temperature ranged from slightly alkaline (8.2) to highly alkaline (11.5) across a wide variety of feedstocks. Biochars shows positive effect in the case of acidic soils compared to alkaline soils (Biederman and Harpole, 2013). Biochar addition can reduce the bio-availability of toxic forms of Al, Cu and Mn and increase the availability of essential nutrients such as Na⁺, K⁺, Ca⁺⁺, Mg⁺⁺ and Mo, thereby rendering a favourable environment for plant growth (Atkinson *et al.*, 2010, Naresh Kumar *et al.*, 2018). The study found that among the several treatments, the application of 60 g kg⁻¹ of biochar had the lowest exchangeable acidity. This was followed by the application of 4 g kg⁻¹ of lime to the soil, while the control group had the highest exchangeable acidity without biochar and lime application. This might be due to the soluble and exchangeable Al₃⁺ precipitates as insoluble hydroxyl Al-species at higher pH condition. Apart from increasing the incorporation of biochar to acidic soil can release their base cations which can participate in exchange reactions and replace the exchangeable Fe₃⁺, Al₃⁺ and H⁺ on the soil surface and decrease the soil exchangeable acidity. Biochar can serve as a liming agent resulting in increased pH and nutrient availability for a different soil (Lehmann and Joseph 2007).

Biochar application on crop yield-

The impact of biochar on crop yield is mostly dependent on the types of soil and the amount of biochar applied. It is a positive effect on crop yield in general and it is more effective when applied to low to medium fertile soils (Chen *et al.*, 2019). Liu *et al.* (2017) reviewed published data from 59 pot experiments and 57 field experiments from 21 countries and found crop productivity was increased by 11% on average. Liu

discovered benefits at field application rates typically less than 30 t ha⁻¹, and reported that increases in crop productivity varied by crop type, with legume crops (30%), vegetables (29%), and grasses (14%), outperforming cereal crops corn (8%), wheat (11%), and rice (7%). Higher biochar application rates combined with NPK fertilizer increased crop yield in tropical Amazonian soils (Steiner et al., 2007) and semi-arid Australian soils (Ogawa, 1994). Major et al., (2010) conducted a multiyear experiment in a maize - soybean rotation system and found that the maize yield was increased by 28 to 30 per cent in two years continuously cultivation.

Carbon sequestration-

When biochar is put to soil, it benefits crop growth; also, biochar includes stable carbon (C), which remains sequestered for much longer periods than it would in the original biomass from which biochar was created. The biochar can rapidly increase the recalcitrant soil Carbon fraction of soil. Biochar also contains varying concentrations of other elements such as Oxygen (O), Hydrogen (H), Nitrogen (N), Sulfur (S), Phosphors (P), base cations and heavy metals (Segun et al., 2019). After three years of experimentation in Alfisol, the application of biochar had a significant impact on soil OC content; at the end of the experiment, the control soil had only 3.6 g kg⁻¹ OC, whereas the soils that received different sources of biochar had soil OC content ranging from 4.4 to 4.8 g kg⁻¹. Increase in the levels of biochar increased the content of OC, WSC (73%) and BMC (37%) in studied soil. (Kannan Pandian et al., 2016).

Biochar addition appears to improve overall plant growth and soil nutritional status while decreasing N₂O emissions. Its amendment reduced CO₂ production for all amendment levels tested (2, 5, 10%, 20, 40 and 60% weight by weight basis; corresponding to 24 to 720 t ha⁻¹ field application rates). The recalcitrance of the biochar suggested that it could be a viable carbon sequestration strategy and might provide substantial net GHG benefits with long lasting reductions in N₂O production. Biochar has potential to mitigate climate change as maximum of 1.8 mt of CO₂ equivalents per year without affecting food security and ecosystem. This is equivalent to 12% of current anthropogenic CO₂ emissions annually (Woolf et al., 2010). The extent of this stimulation varies according to different estimates, being larger up to 60% in forest and smaller about 14% for pastures and crops. The longevity of char in soil, the avoided rate of greenhouse gas emissions, the amount of biochar that can be added to soils, and the amount of biochar that can be produced in an environmentally and economically responsible manner are the four factors that need to be taken into account in order to determine the potential for sequestering carbon from soil additions.

Effect of biochar application Adverse effect-

At this high application rate, yields dropped to the level of the unmodified control. This is a significant sum that is unlikely to be practicable in the field, at least for a one-time change. However, Asai et al. (2009), working in Laos, showed higher upland rice yields with 4 t ha⁻¹ biochar, but yields were unchanged when 8 or 16 t ha⁻¹ were treated. A more recent field study on a poor, acidic soil in the United States found that applying peanut hull and pinechip biochar at 11 and 22 t ha⁻¹ reduced corn yields below those observed in control plots under regular fertilizer management (Gaskin et al., 2010).

Residual effect-

A mycorrhizal bioassay was used to evaluate the residual effects of mineral fertilizers and biochar on soil that was taken from the field trial two years after the biochar was applied. Biochar and both fertilizers increased mycorrhizal colonisation in clover bioassay plants. Deep-banded biochar created favorable circumstances for mycorrhizal fungi to colonize plant roots (Sdaiman et al., 2010). The application of biochar at 0, 5, 10, and 20 g kg⁻¹ soil with and without 5 g kg⁻¹ of dried swine

manure resulted in a significant decrease in the total amount of N, P, Mg, and Si that leached from the manure amended columns as biochar rates increased; however, among columns receiving manure, the 20 kg ha⁻¹ biochar treatments reduced total N and total dissolved P leaching by 11% and 69%, respectively (Laird et al., 2010).

Conclusion

The idea of soil health has raised awareness among horticulturists and farmers of the significance of preserving environmental quality, crop productivity, and soil fertility over an extended period of time. Biochar has positive effects on the physico-chemical and biological properties of soil, which means soil health directly and indirectly influenced with the application of biochar. The application of biochar to soils has several benefits, such as increased soil microbial diversity, reduced soil acidity, improved nutrient uptake efficiency, improved water retention capacity, reduced emission of non-CO₂ greenhouse gases (CH₄, N₂O), and preservation of nutrients and cation exchange capacity.

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